

Evaluating the Consumption of Non-Home Prepared Food in Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the consumption of non-home prepared food in Anambra State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study is to assess the determinants of consumption of non-home prepared food in Anambra State and to ascertain the economic importance of non home prepared food in Anambra State. Primary source of that collection was employed in this study through administration of a well structured Questionnaire. The statistical tools used in this study include the frequency distribution, percentage distribution, descriptive analysis and Chi-square analysis. The findings of this study that sex, age, marital status, occupation, and average monthly income has significant impact on patronage of non-home prepared food. It was found that more males patronize non-home prepared food than females. Also, findings showed that as the age grade increases patronage of non-home prepared food decreases. It was found that single respondents often patronize non-home prepared food than married respondents. Further findings showed that non salary earners equally patronize non-home prepared food than salary earners. Also, findings showed that respondents with less than 10000 average monthly income patronize non-home prepared food mostly followed by respondents with 10000 to 19000 average monthly income. This result indicates that as average monthly income increases, patronage of non-home prepared food decreases. However, findings revealed that non-home prepared food does not significantly impact on the economy of Anambra State.

Keywords: Age, Food, Monthly Income, Occupation, Sex, Patronage,

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the sensitivity of the issue of food consumption, it has been a subject of research interest all over the world, especially meaningful in developing countries where food expenditures contributes to relatively large share of household income. Studies of food consumption cuts across food-related nutritional policies and many others. In such situations, estimates of how food consumption is affected by changes in prices, income, and taxation policies are usually provided (Dunne and Edkins, 2005).

Food consumption in Nigeria has been an important issue, not only because it is related to poverty and food security, but because it is highly associated with living standards and household resource. Essentially, the demand for food depends on population and the dietary habits/per capita daily calorie intake of the people under consideration. On the other hand, the food requirement of the nation is dependent on an additional factors such as food import and export balance. Some researchers believe that on the national level, per-capita growth of production of major foods in Nigeria has not been sufficient to satisfy the demands of an increasing population (Kormawa, 1999). This implies the existence of a wide gap between national supply and national demand for food. Household food consumption pattern in Nigeria has been changing over the last few years. There has been an increase in the consumption of carbohydrate foods like yam, cassava, maize and rice and some decrease in the

consumption of such food items as fish, fresh fruits, as well as fresh and processed vegetables.

Akinyele (2009) argued that the problem of food and nutrition security in Nigeria has not been adequately and critically analyzed, despite various approaches addressing the challenge. He noted that the enormous amount of money spent in attempting to ensure the food security of Nigerians without success calls for a fundamental review of the past approaches and achievements to see what lessons can be learned to re-strategize and to develop an approach that will ensure that better progress is made toward achieving the first Millennium Development Goal. Since the majority of Nigerians (70 percent) live in rural areas, an analysis of the food and nutrition security status of rural dwellers will provide a clear picture of what needs to be done to ensure food security in Nigeria with the attendant improvements in nutrition status when all the other necessary conditions, such as adequate health and care, are present. However, one of the most remarkable social changes in Nigeria since the turn of this century has been the rapid rate of urbanization. However, the major consequence of this has been the creation of a number of social, environmental and economic problems. The most critical among the social problems has been the inability of the country to provide adequate housing especially for average Nigerians. In this view, the constant attempt by both the public and private developers to solve the housing problems leads to the sub-urban residential developers in major cities. The resultant effect of this is reflected in the very wide separation between the places of residence and those of work and schools. This coupled with long hours at work or school and the insufficient or inadequate transportation system, most Nigerians had to rely on the consumption of foods prepared outside the home.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the various determinants of non-home prepared food in Anambra State-Nigeria with the

specific objective to: assess the determinants of consumption of non-home prepared food in Anambra State, and ascertain the economic importance of non home prepared food in Anambra State

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Food security as defined by FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) (1999) refers to the condition in which all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life.

Akinyele (2009) opined that the accessibility of food has three components which comprises of physical access to food, economic access to food, and sustainable access to food. He explained further that availability of food, stability of food supplies and access are therefore three essential determinants of food security. Physical access implies food availability or food supply to the household, as there might be food available at the national level which however may not trickle down to the household level.

Speaking on the economic importance of non-home prepared foods, Tinker and Fruge (1982) opined that most street food enterprises are single person or household-based. They explained that past studies has revealed that most vendors owned only one stall or cart (only 12 per cent owned two and very few more than two), and most received assistance, either from family members (45 percent), paid workers (8 percent) or both (19 percent). However, it is important to observe that the street food trade is both retail and a productive activity: although the sale of street foods is the most visible part of the trade, most street foods have been processed to some extent, much of which may have occurred unseen off-street. In addition, the extent to which foods are processed, and by whom, varies; some street food vendors also provide an outlet for foods processed by others in the informal sector, and also, in

some countries, for small- and large-scale food processing industries in the formal sector.

Bueno (1988) speaking on cost and availability of non-home prepared foods, noted that one of the common prejudices held against street foods is that they are less nutritious and more costly than foods prepared at home. Also, due to the sometimes high costs of fuel and ingredients in urban contexts, economies of scale can create a street food cheaper than the same food prepared at home. Broader economic factors can also affect the cost of street foods relative to home-prepared foods; in most developing nations the effect of economic recession led to an increased consumption of street foods because of the scarcity and high cost of obtaining ingredients. He equally noted that a rise in consumption of street foods following the implementation of structural adjustment programs including currency devaluation in countries like Nigeria.

Stewart et al. (2004) on the contributions of environmental and societal changes on the increasing demand of away from home prepared food, explained that there has been an increase in the consumption of away-from-home food in countries like the United States and equally developing nations across the world. As depicted from the result of their study, they found that in United States the percentage of the food budget spent on away-from home food has steadily increased since the mid-1970s. Consequently, the proportion of calories provided by away-from-home food has increased in recent decades. In 1995, it accounted for 34% of total energy intake, an increase from 18% in 1977–1978. A variety of factors may be contributing to the increased consumption of away-from-home food. The total number of foodservice establishments in the United States has almost doubled in the last three decades, increasing from 491,000 in 1972 to 878,000 in 2004. Furthermore, changes in the workforce, including a rise in dual-income households and women working outside the

home have coincided with the demand for take-out meals and convenience in food preparation. Regardless these causes aforementioned, they noted that away-from-home food is and will continue to be an important part of the U. S. diet.

Igbokwe (2005) opined that fast food business in Nigeria over the years has been on an increasing demand. He noted that the business keeps expanding and gaining new outlets and many Nigerians have either established or are planning to establish a fast food business as source of livelihood. The author argued that most companies and individuals who are in the fast food business may have realized the place of food as one of the basic necessities of man and the business will become a goldmine if well managed.

Reit et al.(2003) in their study evaluated the determinants of non-home-prepared food consumption in two low-income areas in Nairobi. The survey included 241 men and 254 women using a structured questionnaire to obtain data on demographic and socioeconomic factors. The findings of the study revealed that for women in the slum area, the presence of school-age children and distance to work were determinants of non-home-prepared food consumption, whereas employment status and distance to work were determinants for men in the slum area. Having their own income and, for those employed, employment status were determinants for women in the low- to middle-income area, whereas socioeconomic status was the determinant for the men.

Findings from Aromolaran (2004) showed that the negative effect of women's income share on calorie intake of household members cannot be said to be due to a higher cost of obtaining same quantity/quality of food from women's predominantly off-farm income and men's predominantly farm income (called transaction cost). Equally, observed was that the estimated negative effect of increasing women's share of income on calorie intake

is not the consequence of reallocation of women's income from low quality/high calorie foods to high quality/low calorie foods. Further findings from the study support the fact that calorie intake increases in household income is small and close to zero. This implies that income policies may not be the most effective way to achieve substantial improvements in calorie intake levels. Also, it was found that increases in women's share of household income are likely to result in marginal declines in food calorie intake by individual household members. This assertion does not in any way support the general thinking that intra-household resource reallocation from men to women would increase food energy intake. Rather it would imply that food calorie intake by household members is enhanced with more income in the hands of men relative to women.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Research Design and Sample Population

The study adopted the use of survey design method in the conduct of this study. The choice of the survey design was to enable the researcher gather a wide range of relevant data adequate for proving inference for the study. In this study, 400 respondents were randomly selected in Awka the capital of Anambra State between the period July 2018 to December 2018. Awka capital comprises of the following towns : Awka, Nibo, Amawbia, Nise, Umuawulu, Mbaukwu and Isiagwu.

3.2 Method of Data Analysis

The statistical tools used in this study include the frequency distribution, percentage distribution, descriptive analysis, Kruskal Wallis Analysis, and Chi-square analysis. The choice of these tools is to enable the researcher obtain adequate inference on the various objectives of the study.

The respondents comprises of 35% of males and 65% females, respondents 72.5% are single while 27.5% are married,

12.5% are within age group 0-19 years, 77.5% are within age group 20-39 years, 10.0% are within 40-59 years while 0.0% are >59 years. It was also found that 15.0% have no formal education, 2.5% have primary education, 10.0% have secondary education, 72.5% have tertiary education. It was observed that 40.0% are salary earners while 60.0% are non salary earners. The analysis showed the distribution of house size to be 22.5% have 1-3 household size, 55.0% have 4-6 household size, 12.5% have 7-9 household size and 10.0% have >13 household size. It was observed that 42.5% of the respondents earn on the average <10000 naira, 25.0% earn 10000 - 19000, 7.5% earn 20000-39000 and 25.0% ear >40000.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Summary of Demographic response of the respondents

Item	Frequency (%)	Percent
SEX		
FEMALE	260 (65.0)	65.0
MALE	140 (35.0)	35.0
AGE		
0-19	50 (12.5)	12.5
20-39	310 (77.5)	77.5
40-59	40 (10.0)	10.0
> 59	0 (0.0)	0.0
MARITAL STATUS		
SINGLE	290 (72.5)	72.5
MARRIED	110 (27.5)	27.5
EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION		
NO FORMAL EDUCATION	60 (15.0)	15.0
PRIMARY	10 (2.5)	2.5
SECONDARY	40 (10.0)	10.0
TERTIARY	290 (72.5)	72.5

4.1 Chi-square analysis on the effect of sex on patronage of non-home prepared food

H₀₀: Sex has no significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food

Table 2: Result of Chi-Square analysis on the effect of sex on patronage of non-home prepared food

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.396 ^a	1	.036
N of Valid Cases ^b	400		

Figure 1: Distribution of responses on patronage of non-home prepared food by sex

The result obtained in table 2 found a Chi-square value of 4.40 and a p-value of 0.04 which falls on the rejection region of the hypothesis assuming a 95% confidence level. This result implies that sex has significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food. Also, result presented in figure 1 showed that more males patronize non-home prepared food than females.

4.2 Analysis on the effect of Age grade on patronage of non-home prepared food

H₀₁: Age has no significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food

Table 3: Result of Chi-Square Analysis on the effect of Age grade on patronage of non-home prepared food

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	91.028 ^a	2	.000
N of Valid Cases	400		

Figure 2: Distribution of responses on patronage of non-home prepared food by age grade

The result of the analysis obtained in table 3 found a Chi-square value of 91.03 and a p-value of 0.00 which falls on the rejection region of the hypothesis assuming a 95% confidence level. This result implies that age has significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food. Also, it was obtained in figure 2 that as the age grade increases patronage of non-home prepared food decreases.

4.3 Analysis on the impact of Marital Status on patronage of non-home prepared food

H₀₂: Marital Status has no significant impact on patronage of non-home prepared food

Table 4: Result of Chi-square analysis on the impact of Marital Status on patronage of non-home prepared food

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.392 ^a	1	.000
N of Valid Cases ^b	400		

Figure 3: Distribution of responses on patronage of non-home prepared food by marital status

The result of the analysis obtained in table 4 found a Chi-square value of 25.39 and a p-value of 0.00 which falls on the rejection region of the hypothesis assuming a 95% confidence level. This result implies that marital status has significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food. Also, it was found in figure 3 that single respondents patronize non-home prepared food than married respondents.

4.4 Analysis on the effect of Age grade on patronage of non-home prepared food

H₀₃: Occupation has no significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food

Table 5: Result of Chi-square Analysis on the effect of Age grade on patronage of non-home prepared food

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.094 ^a	1	.000
N of Valid Cases ^b	400		

Figure 4: Distribution of responses on patronage of non-home prepared food by occupation

The result of the analysis obtained in table 5 found a Chi-square value of 21.09 and a p-value of 0.00 which falls on the rejection region of the hypothesis assuming a 95% confidence level. This result implies that occupation has significant impact on patronage of non-home prepared food. Also, the result presented in figure 4 showed that non salary earners patronize non-home prepared food than salary earners.

4.5 Analysis on the effect of average monthly income on patronage of non-home prepared food

H₀₄: Average monthly income has no significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food

Table 6: Result of Chi-square Analysis on the effect of average monthly income on patronage of non-home prepared food

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	49.510 ^a	3	.000
N of Valid Cases	400		

The result of the analysis obtained in table 6 found a Chi-square value of 49.51 and a p-value of 0.00 which falls on the rejection region of the hypothesis assuming a 95% confidence level.

Figure 5: Distribution of responses on patronage of non-home prepared food by average monthly income

This result implies that average income has significant effect on patronage of non-home prepared food. Also, it was observed in figure 5 that respondents with less than 10000 average monthly income patronize non-home prepared food mostly followed by respondents with 10000 to 19000 average monthly income. This result indicates that as average monthly income increases, patronage of non-home prepared food decreases.

4.6 Kruskal-Wallis Test on whether non-home prepared food has positive impact on the economy

H₀₅: Non-home prepared food has no positive impact on the economy

Table 7: Test Statistics Result on whether non-home prepared food has positive impact on the economy

	Response on economic importance of non-home prepared food
Chi-Square	7.250
df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.123
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variable: Option	

The result of the analysis obtained in table 7 found a Chi-square value of 7.25 and a p-value of 0.12 which falls on the acceptance region of the hypothesis assuming a 95% confidence level. This result implies that non-home prepared food has no positive impact on the economy of Anambra State.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines the consumption of non-home prepared food in

Anambra State, Nigeria. Food choices can differ with regards to some certain factors such as sex, age, cultural food consumption pattern and settlements.

The findings of this study that sex, age, marital status, occupation, and average monthly income has significant impact on patronage of non-home prepared food. It was found that more males patronize non-home prepared food than females. Also, findings showed that as the age grade increases patronage of non-home prepared food decreases. It was found that single respondents often patronize non-home prepared food than married respondents. Further findings showed that non salary earners equally patronize non-home prepared food than salary earners.

Also, findings showed that respondents with less than 10000 average monthly income patronize non-home prepared food mostly followed by respondents with 10000 to 19000 average monthly income. This result indicates that as average monthly income increases, patronage of non-home prepared food decreases. However, findings revealed that non-home prepared food does not significantly impact on the economy of Anambra State. This could be attributed to the quality of non-home prepared food sold in Anambra State which might not be satisfactory people who are mostly civil servants.

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